

Effect of Monitoring and Evaluations Practices on Performance of Milk Processing Firms in Nairobi County

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Abstract:

The study was conducted in an attempt to establish the effect of monitoring and evaluations practices on performance milk processing firms in Nairobi County. The study was informed by Resource-Based Theory, Theory of Change and Agency Theory. The research design used in this study was descriptive research design. The target population was 262 employees drawn from 8 milk processing firms within Nairobi County. Stratified simple random was used to select a sample size of 122 firms. The research focused on primary data that was collected from questionnaires. The researcher used the Cronbach's Alpha to assess internal consistency reliability for the five-point Likert scale items with 0.7 and above being the cut-off point or acceptable range. The study used descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse the quantitative data. The results indicated that data demand and use ($\beta = 0.034, p < 0.05$) and research and surveillance ($\beta = 0.292, p < 0.05$) had a positive and significant effect on firm performance. It was therefore recommended that manufacturing firms define issues in consultation with stakeholders so as to ensure that project objective are clearly stated, understood and supported by all. There should also be a close working relationship between Monitoring & Evaluation and capacity building activities so as to enhance firm performance. Besides, it is crucial for firms to collect and analyze data on customers so as to have an idea on areas to improve on. Finally, it is important to have a special focus on customers while engaging in research and surveillance.

Keywords; data demand and use, research and surveillance, firm performance, Monitoring & Evaluation

Introduction

Modern day businesses have to develop strategies actively to keep ahead of the dynamism of the changes in their operating environment. Active improvement of strategies helps firms maintain the flexibility necessary to navigate the intricacies brought on about by shifting consumer needs and increasing competition (Goksoy, 2013). As such, developing unique and practical improvements to their products and services that increase the utility their clients derive from them improves a firm's competitiveness (Peteraf and Barney, 2003 p.314). Sustaining these advantages improves a company's planning and accomplishment of its short-term goals while ensuring it maintains a positive outlook on its long-term performance especially for smaller firms that have to be frugal with their resources.

To keep track of both the changes in their environment and those caused inadvertently by the improvements they make in their operations, companies need to develop their monitoring and evaluation functions (Baraka, cited in Kibet, Makokha, & Namusonge, 2016). The ability to measure and track progress and impact helps companies to adopt Result-Based Management strategies that improve their overall objectivity during planning and decision-making (Waren, cited in Thuita & Kibati, 2016). Most large companies use customer experience surveys to gauge their satisfaction levels with the level of service they receive and elicit information into how they can improve both their products and service delivery (Janković, Marković and Brnad, 2014). The information generated from these surveys also provide them with insights into consumer trends and help them adapt their products and services accordingly, therefore, ensuring the continuity of their revenues. As such, investing in monitoring and evaluation has significant benefits to the overall performance of a firm especially in

the long-term by ensuring that it remains focused on its overall goals and objectives and enhances its ability and capacity to learn and evolve organically (IFRC, 2011).

The ever-increasing competition in the business arena necessitates that companies strive to develop unique advantages to help them stay ahead of their competition and attain revenues and profits. Active monitoring and evaluation provide companies with the tools to be flexible to the changes in both their environment and the systems brought about by the improvements they institute in their processes (Shamsi and Syed, 2015). It is especially important for new entrants into relatively established industries such as the manufacturing sector in Kenya because of the tight control older more experienced firms have on the market (OECD, 2010). In addition, the pressure is higher in companies in developing countries because they have to compete with products from their more established and sophisticated counterparts in more industrialized countries (Kam, 2012). Therefore, they have to work on developing strong cultures rooted in monitoring and evaluation to ensure that they maintain sustainable high response times to changes in their environment while mitigating any unforeseen and unprecedented problems and challenges that might result from changes to their operations. The benefits companies can reap from effective monitoring and evaluation because of the experiential knowledge gains from the resulting learning curves (UNESCO, 2014; Muchelule; Musomba, 2013; Kimweli, 2013; Ramadhan, 2014; Muzinda, 2007, Ogomoditse, 2012; Afsah, 2007; Richard, 2009; Indrakumaran, 2011; Clear, 2009; Ogweno, 2012, Fazli, 2012).

Theoretical Literature Review

This section explores theories from previous studies and research to conceptualize its assumptions and arguments as it seeks to prove the validity or otherwise of its hypothesis. It focused on three theories namely resource-based theory. Resource-based theory bases its arguments on the premise that organizations are a combination of several groups of resources that create value for their stakeholders when coordinated properly (Roos and Roos, 1997; Barnet, 1991). As such, companies that outperform the competitors in their spaces are those that can develop and maintain unique attributes or sets of attributes that give them a better performance than their competitors (Hijzen, Görg& Hine, 2005; Conner, 1991).

Optimal use of the resources available to an organization is only possible if all its levels of management and employees work together in concert to identify any challenges and problems their processes can inadvertently create (Chandler, 1990). Not only can this synchronous association improve performance, but it should also create significant process efficiencies resulting in considerable cost and time efficiencies allowing companies to offer their products at lower prices (Chandler, 1990). In addition, the resulting closed loop processes result in better retention of proprietary resource, system and process advantages further improve the uniqueness of a company's competitive edge (Barney, 1986). The resulting high performance should also increase employee morale and therefore remove the weak link that is the human factor in many organizations especially through knowledge drain (Hamel and Prahalad, 1996).

Literature Review

Data use demand

Data use and demand is a key practice of Monitoring & Evaluation. However, Mackay (2007) notes that poor monitoring infrastructure and policies in many African countries increase their difficulty to collect and qualify performance data. Ibrahim (2007), in support of this, notes that the problem with these countries often lies in their lack of analytical skills and experience which denies them of the benefits of learning from experience. According to Kuzek and Rist (2004), some developing countries collect a lot of data that cannot be put to use. Until recently in Moldova, the system performed poorly because of low demand for the generation and use of

information to advise decision-making processes resulting in confusion from the oversupply of data (Marie-Helene & Dennis, 2008). Lack of clarity concerning the end users leads to the collection of the excessive amount of data that does not help (Guijt, 1999). There is a need to pay more attention to timeliness when releasing Monitoring & Evaluation findings in order to ensure they help to alleviate the problem of relevance (Segone, 2008). To mitigate the inherent challenges indicators should be distributed appropriately in tandem with what they are required to measure; the input, activities, output, outcomes or impact.

The indicators should also be specified in terms of quality, time, target group and place (Nuguti, 2009). In China, lower levels of project management office only collected and tabulated data and passed it up to the next level without analysing or reflecting on their own data. This was an impediment. At the same time, project management offices suffered from too much data which impacted the analysis and led to a review of monitoring data only once annually (China Watershed Management Project Report, 2006). Therefore, there is need to use credible data for ease of use. Firms consciously develop objective indicators for the continued performance evaluation of the project long after its completion and commissioning (Gusfield, 1975). According to Potter *et al.* (2006), many M&E systems are complex and attempt to monitor too many issues.

Further, Potter *et al.* (2006) recommend that Monitoring & Evaluation systems should be technically simplified and made user friendly, or else organizations run the risk of continued poor data quality (Riddell *et al.*, 1997). Mutua (2013) notes there is need to train various committees involved in Monitoring & Evaluation data collection and analysis regarding improvement in communication modalities. Monitoring & Evaluation processes should develop actionable insights that should increase organization performance and improve good governance and oversight.

In many countries, low demand for performance data is an especially difficult problem for the development of good Monitoring & Evaluation (Mackay, 2007). Collection of too much data is a problem and may result in a situation where the inclination to provide quality data is low because of the lack of incentive. There is a need to develop frameworks and baselines to guide the development of proactive evaluation systems to increase the demand for quality data (Mackay, 2007). Clearly, not many government officials have any background in data collection and analysis (Kusek & Rist, 2004).

Ultimately, the success of performance management processes depends on the level of integration of all the stakeholders affected by the phenomena under evaluation and the insights their study will have. Active participation increases their investment in the process and its adoption and use of the information it generates. They should be constantly briefed and given an opportunity to respond before the conclusion of the process (Bamberger, 2008). There is a need to look into the demand for data critically and to establish the extent of use and the specific ways of utilization. However, more governments fast realize the benefits that are having an encouraging performance management processes (Mackay, 2007).

The primary purpose of Monitoring & Evaluation data demand is to promote accountability and transparency in management and strategy development. Monitoring & Evaluation data uses standardized methods and techniques to enhance management decision-making processes and communication with stakeholders (Vernon, 2001). Establishing baselines is an important phase of performance management and is instrumental in ensuring the success of the endeavor (Kusek and Rist, 2004). The importance is underpinned by the fact that the objectivity of performance management is only possible if the progress has an origin to be measured against. While this might be difficult, historical data can provide insights into how to improve the objectivity and flexibility of the performance management processes by selecting the most impartial indicators. Although it is tempting to set comparatively low targets to ensure they are reached, the setting of targets that are high enough is of the essence to ensure project execution impetus.

Focusing on higher level project results must not overlook the short-term performance objectives especially in the face of increasing difficulties in managing scarce resources effectively. It is, therefore, important that frameworks and policies develop the flexibility of evaluation processes to maintain a holistic view of processes. A broader perspective on performance helps organizations design better systems and perform better in the long-term by learning from challenges and problems opening them up to realize and take advantage of opportunities in their environments (Jim, 2007).

Surveillance

Tuckermann (2007) observes that the project team he studied did not recognize Monitoring & Evaluation as a learning tool, believing that the results could be used against their work: Monitoring & Evaluation was perceived as opening room for criticism regarding performance, putting their knowledge and status at risk. Further, King and Volkov, (2005) note that Monitoring & Evaluation should not only be used for accountability and transparency but should constitute a critical inquiry as well. There is need to ask critical questions and avoid focusing on the description of activities and recording of the number of those served (Khan, 2003).

This is an issue that research and surveillance could effectively address. Due to inadequate extension services, production is very low, and an increasing number of African countries cannot feed themselves (Mazibuko, 2007).

In some cases, information provided by Monitoring & Evaluation influences decision-making neither during implementation nor during the planning of an on-going project development and new initiatives (Britton, 2005). All this implies that such reports do not have a bearing on the sustainability of projects. Karanja (2013), research on the sustainability of youth income generating projects in Kangema District, Murang'a County, Kenya, have found that majority of the youth projects are only evaluated twice a year, and 23% have not been evaluated at all. The study recommends that Periodic Monitoring & Evaluation by experts from the Ministry of Youth or any other agency should be incorporated to boost the Monitoring & Evaluation of these projects and enhance the quality of the projects. The author further recommends the need for those concerned with these youth projects to involve professional or experts in the management of youth projects, particularly during planning, implementation, and Monitoring & Evaluation phases. There is need to carry out further studies on the challenges facing the field staff working in community-based projects in undertaking Monitoring & Evaluation activities so as to bring out factors that need to be considered ardently regarding such projects, and hence realize effective outcomes from the projects (Mugambi & Kanda, 2013).

Project Monitoring & Evaluation surveillance is an on-going process, especially for projects of a pilot or innovative nature. Both must go hand in hand with determining the project's Monitoring & Evaluation requirements realistically. Of invaluable use to this process is the log frame matrix. Establishing the means-ends linkages along the entire results chain, especially assessing the adequacy of interventions and the reasonableness of assumptions in relation to project objectives, are key aspects of project design that ought not to be buffed over. Availability of the log frame at the start of the project also helps link successive annual work planning and budgeting processes to the overall project plan and information gathering and reporting requirements (Jim, 2007).

Key to effective project Monitoring & Evaluation surveillance is investing adequate time and resources in system design at the outset, with provision for refinement and evolution over the course of implementation. It generally requires the inclusion of an experienced individual to undertake this task as a core member of the project preparation/appraisal team. Essential features of the Monitoring & Evaluation framework to be elaborated include: An all-inclusive Monitoring & Evaluation strategy, including an impact evaluation strategy, clearly showing roles and responsibilities of implementing and coordinating agencies and, where applicable,

community based organizations, information requirements, specific tools and methodologies for data collection, analysis and reporting, and the necessary institutional arrangements, including well-designed linkages with management units and steering committees (USAID, 2000).

Project Monitoring & Evaluation surveillance requires a set of component-specific performance indicators for the entire results chain – distinguishing among input, output and outcome indicators, to measure success or failure in achieving each component's results. As part of the participatory approach, several iterations, involving a series of stakeholder consultations may be necessary to agree on the indicators. Precise targets, especially quantitative ones, and timelines may have to be decided on only at the time of project commencement or during execution, in concurrence with annual work planning (Woodhill, 2007).

The operational objectives of the Monitoring & Evaluation surveillance system are an integral part of the Monitoring & Evaluation framework which leads to the sustainability of the projects. These will need to be specified, and agreement sought amongst project stakeholders. They should ideally be accompanied by a set of Monitoring & Evaluation system outcomes – which are subject to monitoring, as for any other project component. For instance, the systematic provision of information for control and coordination of implementation may be one operational objective, whereas timely identification of execution constraints and development opportunities could be the desired outcome (IFAD, 2002).

Research Gap

Concern about the absence of effective monitoring and evaluation in regard to factors such as data use, planning, research, and surveillance means that there is a high likelihood of influence by these factors on the effectiveness of the system and process. Evidence from literature points out that in Sub-Saharan Africa substantial M&E achievements in large manufacturing on the ground are rare. Most studies done in Kenya focus on specific projects or specific areas and therefore makes it difficult to generalize to large organizations' projects and this study attempts to fill the gap. The study, therefore, focused on establishing this influence and tried to give an insight, hence justifying this research.

Material and methods

The research design to be used in this study was descriptive research design in nature which found the solution to the study problem. The target population was 262 employees drawn from 8 milk processing firms within Nairobi County namely; Brookside, New KCC, Sameer Agriculture & Livestock, Bio food product, Orchard Limited, Lattana, Eldoville Dairy, and Kinangop Dairy Ltd. From the 8 firms HR database, there are a total of 262 employees of the 8 milk processing firms. Simple random sampling was used in this study to select individual employees. In the event that irregular testing is utilized in the investigation, every individual from the populace or of subgroups has an equivalent possibility of being chosen as different individuals from a similar gathering (Shampoo and Resnik, 2003). The inclination is dodged in irregular examining, in light of the fact that there is a high likelihood that all the populace qualities were spoken to in the example. The researcher used the Cronbach's Alpha to assess internal consistency reliability for the five-point likert scale items with 0.7 and above being the cut-off point or acceptable range. The goal of this is to design a reliable instrument for scores on similar items to be related, but for each to contribute some unique information as well. This study utilized the SPSS software to perform correlation and regression analysis on the collected data as it is possible to relate the dependent variable with multiple variables. The regression equation is a function of variables x and β

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where, y = performance of milk processing firms, α = constant.

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_3$ = the slope which represents the degree in which sustainable performance changes as the independent variable change by one unit variable. x_1 = Monitoring & Evaluation data demand & use, x_2 = Research & surveillance in Monitoring & Evaluation

Findings and Discussions

Out of the 122 questionnaires administered, 98 questionnaires were retrieved making a response rate of 80.3%. According to Sekaran & Uma (2013) response rate of 30% is acceptable for surveys and therefore the response rate for this study is sufficient for further analysis. the Cronbach alpha values range between 0.747 to 0.945. According to Hair *et al.* (2010), values of above 0.6 are acceptable. From the findings on reliability, the level of reliability was sufficient thus the level of internal consistency was acceptable.

Descriptive statistics

Through Data Demand & Use, individuals are able to acquire specific knowledge and skills required to undertake a given task. The study, therefore, sought to ascertain the effect of data use demand on the performance of performance of manufacturing firms in Nairobi County. the findings on Data Demand & Use had an aggregate mean of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 0.53. The results suggest that the respondents were not entirely in agreement with the items on Data Demand & Use. the findings on research & surveillance summed up to a mean of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 0.65 suggesting that the respondents were not entirely in agreement with the items on research & surveillance. In general, the results on firm performance had an aggregate mean of 4.09 and a standard deviation of 0.68. The results suggest that there is an increase in firm performance. There were also fewer variations in the responses. a strong relationship was exhibited between Data Demand & Use and firm performance ($r = 0.535$, p -value $< .01$). Finally, there was a strong relationship between Research & Surveillance and firm performance ($r = 0.562$, p -value $< .01$).

Table 1; Descriptive statistics

	Mean	SD	Firm performance	Data Demand & Use	Research & Surveillance
Firm performance	4.09	0.68	1		
Data Demand & Use	3.77	0.53	.535**	1	
Research & Surveillance	3.78	0.65	.562**	0.192	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Multiple Regression results

Table 1 illustrates the model summary of multiple regression model; the results showed that all the four predictors (project planning, Capacity Building, Data Demand & Use, and Research & Surveillance) explained 53.5 percent variation of firm performance (R squared = 0.535). Study findings in table 2 indicated that the above discussed coefficient of determination was significant as evidence of F ratio of 36.166 with p value 0.000 < 0.05 (level of significance). Thus, the model was fit to predict firm performance using project planning, Capacity Building, Data Demand & Use, and Research & Surveillance.

The third objective of the study sought to ascertain the effect of Data Demand & Use on the performance of performance of manufacturing firms in Nairobi County. Study findings showed that Data Demand & Use had coefficients of the estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_3 = 0.075$ (p -value = 0.034 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) hence Data Demand & Use has a significant effect on firm performance. This indicates that for each unit

increase in Data Demand & Use, there is up to 0.075 units increase in firm performance. The effect of Data Demand & Use is stated by the t-test value = 2.15 which point out that the effect of Data Demand & Use is over 5 times that of the error associated with it. In tally with the findings, Mackay, (2007) argued that systems for data demand and use could help improve performance. Similarly, Vernon, (2001) noted that M & E data is a system which uses formalized procedures to provide the management at all levels with relevant information which is key in enhancing firm performance.

Finally, findings showed that Research & Surveillance had coefficients of the estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_4 = 0.292$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$). This suggests that there is up to 0.292-unit increase in firm performance for each unit increase in Research & Surveillance. The effect of Research & Surveillance is thrice the effect attributed to the error; this is indicated by the t-test value = 3.818. Consistent with the findings, Karanja (2013), noted that there is a need for periodic monitoring and evaluation by experts so as to enhance the quality of projects in the government's sphere. However, Britton, (2005) was of the opinion that the report made during research and surveillance rarely influences decision making hence they have no bearing on the sustainability of projects.

Table 2 Multiple Regression results

	Unstandardized		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	0.223	0.298		0.747	0.457
Data Demand & Use	0.162	0.075	0.186	2.15	0.034
Research & Surveillance	0.306	0.08	0.292	3.818	0.000
mode summary					
R Square	0.535				
Adjusted R Square	0.515				
F	36.166				
Sig.	.000				

a Dependent Variable: Firm performance

Conclusion

The study indicated that data demand and use significantly influences the performance of manufacturing firms. Most often than not, the emphasis is on the quality of data rather than the quantity. There may be too much information which may be irrelevant since the key stakeholders were not actively engaged in acquiring such data. Besides, that, data on its own does not generate much importance, it needs to be analyzed and reflected on so as to develop insights to drive the performance of manufacturing firms.

Research and surveillance are key to the performance of manufacturing firms. The implication is that investing adequate time and resources in project design at the onset with provisions to make refinement over the course of implementation significantly improves the firm performance. Most often than not, the research and surveillance done on both customers and products provide important information that is key in facilitating the firm's competitive advantage. Overall, research and surveillance are necessary for improved firm performance.

Recommendations

There is evidence data demand, and use has a positive and significant influence on firm performance, it is essential to pay more attention to timeliness when releasing of Monitoring & Evaluation findings in order to

ensure they help to alleviate the problem of relevance. It is also crucial for firms to collect and analyze data on customers so as to have an idea on areas to improve on. The collected data should be properly organized and stored so that it can easily be traced for future reference. In addition, there is a need for employee training in data collection so as to enhance the quality of data collected which will in turn increase firm performance. Finally, to improve research and surveillance, it is important to have a special focus on customers while engaging in research and surveillance. It is also crucial that the surveillance on product development is effective. Furthermore, the research and surveillance on the market should be done regularly, and information obtained used in decision making.

Further Research Recommendations

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of monitoring and evaluations practices on the performance of manufacturing firms. a case of milk processing firms in Nairobi county. Valuable insights have been found however it is important to reflect on the conducted work so that further research opportunities can be pointed out. First and foremost, there is a need for further research since there is limited literature on the influence of research and surveillance on firm performance. Also, the study utilizes only primary data. It is therefore recommended that future researchers can extend the study longitudinally based on a survey which is preferable for eliciting more detailed information on a particular subject. Finally, a further study needs to be conducted using more variables that may be relevant to this study since there is no evidence that firm performance of manufacturing firms in Nairobi County is entirely dependent on project planning, capacity building, data demand, and use as well as research and surveillance.

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